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Effect of different muscle contraction mode on the expression of Myostatin, IGF-1, and PGC-1 alpha family members in human vastus lateralis muscle

Abstract:

Muscle contraction stimulates a transient change of myogenic factors, partly related to the mode of contractions. Here, we assessed the response of IGF-1Ea, IGF-1Eb, IGF-1Ec, PGC1 α -1, PGC1 α -4, and myostatin to the eccentric Vs. the concentric contraction in human skeletal muscle. Ten healthy males were performed an acute eccentric and concentric exercise bout (n = 5 per group). For each contraction type, participants performed 12 sets of 10 repetitions knee extension by the dominant leg. Baseline and post-exercise muscle biopsy were taken 4 weeks before and immediately after experimental sessions from Vastus Lateralis muscle. Genes expression was measured by real-time PCR technique. There was a significant increase in PGC1 α -1, PGC1 α -4, IGF-1Ea and, IGF-1Eb mRNA after concentric contraction ($p \leq 0.05$), while the PGC1 α -4 and IGF-1Ec significantly increased after eccentric contraction ($p \leq 0.05$). It is intriguing to highlight that; no significant differences between groups were evident for changes in any variables following exercise bouts ($p \geq 0.05$). Our results found that concentric and eccentric contractions presented different responses in PGC1 α -1, IGF-1Ea, IGF-1Eb, and IGF-1Ec mRNA. However, a similar significant increase in mRNA content was observed in PGC1 α -4. Further, no apparent differences could be found between the response of genes to eccentric and concentric contraction

Keywords: Eccentric contraction, Concentric contraction, Gene expression, PGC-1 alpha, IGF-1, Myostatin

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